

Tracking A General, Frequency Modulated Signal In Noise¹

Tod Luginbuhl
Naval Undersea Warfare Center
Newport, RI 02841-1708 USA
t.e.luginbuhl@ieee.org (EMAIL)

Peter Willett
University of Connecticut
Storrs, CT 06269-2157 USA
willett@enr.uconn.edu (EMAIL)

Abstract

A general, frequency modulated (GFM) signal characterizes the vibrations produced by compressors, turbines, propellers, gears and other rotating machines in a dynamic environment. A GFM signal is defined as the composition of a real or complex, periodic or almost periodic function (the carrier) with a real, differentiable function (the modulation). This paper develops a frequency domain tracking algorithm for a GFM signal in noise using the expectation-maximization (EM) algorithm. The primary advantage of this approach is the ratios (harmonic numbers) of the carrier function do not need to be known a priori. The tracking algorithm exploits knowledge of the noise spectrum so that a separate normalization procedure is not required. The noise spectrum is incorporated into the tracking algorithm in essentially the same way that a clutter or noise model is incorporated into the probabilistic multi-hypothesis tracking algorithm (PMHT). Consequently, the GFM signal tracking algorithm presented in this paper is a PMHT-style algorithm. The algorithm's performance is compared to two other algorithms from the literature using Monte Carlo trials and a simulated signal.

1 Introduction

A GFM signal is a frequency modulated (FM) periodic or almost periodic signal. If the carrier signal is only a single sinusoid, then the GFM signal is also a FM signal. Periodic or harmonic signals and almost periodic signals are important in many areas. In the remainder of this paper, the terms periodic signal and harmonic signal are used for both periodic and almost periodic signals. Measurement and analysis of periodic vibrations is a critical part of machine monitoring. This is particularly true of large, high speed compressors and turbines where bearing failure or coupling failure can result in catastrophic damage to equipment [7]. These signals are of considerable interest to the surveillance community for monitoring marine mammals and shipping traffic. Minimizing and suppressing harmonic signals (harmonic noise) is an important part of alternat-

ing current electrical power transmission and distribution. Harmonic signals also play a critical role in music reproduction and synthesis and in speech recognition and synthesis.

To analyze harmonic signals, it is necessary to measure the amplitude and frequency of the signal's (approximate) Fourier series components. If the signal is truly periodic, then it is only necessary to estimate its fundamental frequency (one over the period), since all other component frequencies are integer multiples (harmonic numbers) of the fundamental frequency. Unfortunately, sensor bandwidth may make it impossible to observe the fundamental frequency of a harmonic signal. This is usually not an issue when using accelerometers to monitor machines because accelerometers can measure vibrations down to zero frequency [7]. However, sensor bandwidth is a necessary reality in surveillance applications. When the fundamental frequency of a periodic signal cannot be observed, it is necessary to measure the frequencies of the observed Fourier components because one can no longer find a unique set of integer multiples and an unobserved fundamental frequency to fit the data. The discussion in this paper assumes that the relationships between the frequencies (harmonic numbers) comprising the signal are not known.

In many applications, the periodic signal of interest is also time varying. Hence, the parameters of signal of interest must be tracked through time as well. In this paper only the frequencies of the Fourier components are assumed to vary with time. For machine analysis problems, a phase referencing sensor can be used to monitor the actual speed of rotation. While such information could be exploited by the methods developed in this paper, it is assumed that this kind of reference signal is not available. The approach taken is to estimate the center or average frequency of each Fourier series component and estimate the modulation separately. It will be shown in a later section that the modulation is common to all of the Fourier series components; hence information from each Fourier series component is used to estimate the modulation.

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2 Previous Work

The problem of estimating the parameters of a periodic signal is not new to the literature. The methods developed by other authors fall into three categories: time domain methods, frequency domain methods and high order spectral techniques. Time domain methods are the most popular. The time domain methods break down into two groups. References [6], [13] and [3] assume that the signal is not time varying, while references [8] and [10] assume that the signal is time varying. The frequency domain approaches described in references [9] and [4] assume that the frequencies comprising the signal are time varying. The high order spectral techniques discussed in references [11], [1] and [15] are really designed to detect phase or frequency dependence between pairs of frequencies, but these methods can be used to estimate parameters as well. The high order spectral techniques assume the frequencies are not time varying.

With the exception of the high order spectral techniques, a major drawback to all the algorithms discussed in the previous paragraph is the algorithms need to know the relationships between the frequencies (i.e. the harmonic numbers). The high order spectral techniques are extremely sensitive to time variation which severely limits their utility. The objective of this paper is to develop an estimator that does not need to know the relationships between the frequency components of a periodic signal and that can track time variations in the frequencies. In the next section, a model of time varying periodic signals is presented that is a natural extension of FM. This model allows one to estimate the parameters of a time varying periodic signal without needing to know the relationship between the frequencies.

3 General FM Processes

A natural way to generalize FM is to allow the carrier signal to be any periodic or almost periodic function. A further generalization of FM comes from thinking of the GFM signal as the composition of the carrier function and the modulation function. Hence, if $s(t)$ is the GFM signal produced by modulating the periodic function $h(t)$ with the message $m(t)$, then $s(t) = h(m(t))$. An example of a GFM is a harmonic series produced by a mechanical system:

$$h(t) = \sum_{l=1}^L A_l \exp [i2\pi f_l m(t) + \theta_l]. \quad (1)$$

If no integer relationship exists between the frequencies, then $h(t)$ is an almost periodic function.

In many cases of practical interest, the modulation sig-

nal varies at a much slower rate than the carrier. When this is true, approximating the modulation function with a continuous, piecewise linear function greatly simplifies analysis of a general, FM signal. In order to develop a piecewise linear approximation to the modulation function $m(t)$, let $J = [0, T]$ be an interval on the real line contained in the domain of m and divide J into Υ consecutive intervals $J_n = [t_n, t_{n+1}]$ for $n = 0, \dots, \Upsilon - 1$. A continuous, piecewise linear approximation to $m(t)$ on J is given by

$$\tilde{m}_\Upsilon(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\Upsilon-1} [\alpha(t_n)t + \beta(t_n)] r\left(\frac{t-t_n}{t_{n+1}-t_n}\right) \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha(t_n) = \frac{m(t_{n+1})-m(t_n)}{t_{n+1}-t_n}$, $\beta(t_n) = m(t_n) - \alpha(t_n)t_n$ and $r(t)$ is the "rectangular window." The modulation signal can be approximated by $\tilde{m}_\Upsilon(t)$ to any degree of accuracy by making Υ sufficiently large. This approximation to the modulation function will be used to find an approximate expression for the discrete-time Fourier transform (DTFT) of a general, FM signal.

To develop an expression for the DTFT of a GFM signal, assume that the modulation function is approximately linear over the intervals $\{[nKT_s, (n+1)KT_s]\}$ (i.e. the distance between the end points of each interval J_n is $t_{n+1} - t_n = KT_s$) where the integer $K > 1$. The sampling period T_s is chosen so that $s(t)$ can be perfectly reconstructed from the sequence of samples $\{s(t_n + jT_s)\}$. The DTFT of s over J_n equals

$$S_n(f) = \sum_{l=1}^L A_l \frac{\sin [K\pi(f_l T_s \alpha(t_n) - f)]}{\sin [\pi(f_l T_s \alpha(t_n) - f)]} e^{i\psi_{lk}(f)} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\psi_{lk}(f) = \theta_l + 2\pi f_l m(t_n) + \pi(K-1)(f_l T_s \alpha(t_n) - f). \quad (4)$$

The amplitude of $S_n(f)$ as a function of frequency depends on a set of constants $\{f_l\}$ and the slope of the modulation function at time t_n . If the frequencies f_1, \dots, f_L are well separated (i.e. more than $2/KT_s$ Hertz apart), then

$$|S_n(f)|^2 \approx \sum_{l=1}^L A_l^2 \frac{\sin^2 [K\pi(f_l T_s \alpha(t_n) - k/K)]}{\sin^2 [\pi(f_l T_s \alpha(t_n) - k/K)]} \quad (5)$$

provided the cross terms are negligible. Therefore, the magnitude square of $S_n(f)$ consists of L trajectories where each trajectory is centered on a frequency f_l , and the path of the all of the trajectories is given by the sequence of slopes of the modulation function. Estimating the frequencies $\{f_l\}$ and the modulation sequence $\{m(t_n)\}$ is a multitarget tracking problem where all the tracks have a common prior or model. An expectation-maximization (EM) estimation algorithm

[2] inspired by the probabilistic multi-hypothesis tracking algorithm described in [12] is derived in reference [5] and is summarized in this paper. Before summarizing this algorithm, the statistical model for this estimation problem is given in the next section.

4 The Statistical Model

Suppose a GFM signal $s(t)$ is contaminated with an independent, complex, finite bandwidth, additive, zero mean noise $\eta(t)$ to form the observed signal $r(t)$. The observed sequence $\{r(t_n + jT_s)\}$ is transformed to the frequency domain by one or more K length discrete Fourier transforms (DFTs). The modulation $m(t)$ of the GFM from interval J_n to interval J_{n+1} is modeled as the output of a discrete time linear system driven by a deterministic control signal and a white Gaussian process noise vector: $a(t_{n+1}) = Aa(t_n) + b(t_n) + q(t_n)$ and $m(t_n) = Ca(t_n)$ where $q(t_n)$ is the Gaussian process noise with covariance Q . For notational purposes, let \mathcal{A} represent the sequence of state variables for the modulation process: $\mathcal{A} = \{a(t_n)\}_{n=0}^{T-1}$. Hence, \mathcal{A} has a Gauss-Markov PDF.

To develop an approximation to the spectrum corresponding to the time interval J_n , let $I = [0, 2\pi]$, and let $\{I_k\}$ partition I into K subintervals. Let $\mathcal{R} = \{R_n\}_{n=0}^{T-1}$ represent the sequence of magnitude square DFTs of length K obtained from $r(t)$. Given the modulation sequence, the magnitude square DFT is conditionally independent. If R_{kn} is quantized to N_{kn} (mapped to the positive integers), then this is approximately the same as observing a total of N_{kn} samples in I_k from the normalized spectrum of r [5]. The PDF of the quantized data \mathcal{N}_n given \mathcal{A} is the multinomial PDF

$$P(\mathcal{N}_n | \alpha(t_n)); \lambda) = \binom{N_n}{N_{0n} \dots N_{K-1n}} \prod_{k=1}^B P_{kn}(\lambda)^{N_{kn}} \quad (6)$$

where

$$P_{kn}(\lambda) \approx \sum_{l=1}^L \pi_l \int_{I_k} p_l(\omega | \alpha(t_n); \lambda_l) d\omega + \pi_\eta \int_{I_k} \tilde{S}_\eta(\omega) d\omega, \quad (7)$$

$p_l(\omega | \alpha(t_n); \lambda_l)$ is Gaussian with mean $\alpha(t_n)\mu_l$ and variance σ_l^2 , and $\tilde{S}_\eta(\omega)$ represents the normalized power spectrum of the noise process η .

5 Estimation Algorithm Summary

Let $\lambda^{(i)}$ denote the parameter estimates after i iterations have been completed. The parameter estimates

for iteration $i + 1$ are obtained from $\lambda^{(i)}$. To simplify the notation, let $W_{kn}^{(i)} = N_{kn}/P_{kn}(\lambda^{(i)})$,

$$w_{ln}^{(i)} = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} W_{kn}^{(i)} \int_{I_k} p_l(\omega | \alpha^{(i)}(t_n); \lambda_l^{(i)}) d\omega, \quad (8)$$

$$u_{ln}^{(i)} = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} W_{kn}^{(i)} \int_{I_k} \omega p_l(\omega | \alpha^{(i)}(t_n); \lambda_l^{(i)}) d\omega \quad (9)$$

and

$$v_{ln}^{(i)} = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} W_{kn}^{(i)} \int_{I_k} (\omega - \alpha^{(i)}(t_n)\mu_l^{(i+1)})^2 p_l(\omega | \alpha^{(i)}(t_n); \lambda_l^{(i)}) d\omega. \quad (10)$$

The mixing proportions (or component probabilities) are updated first because they are independent of the other parameters. The mixing proportions are updated by

$$\pi_l^{(i+1)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{T-1} \pi_l^{(i)} w_{ln}^{(i)}. \quad (11)$$

Updating the remaining parameters is more complicated, because the update equations for $\{\lambda_l\}$ and \mathcal{A} are coupled. Since $\{\lambda_l\}$ and \mathcal{A} cannot be solved for independently, a generalized EM algorithm [2] [14] is used to estimate the parameters. An alternative approach is described in [5].

Specifically, new estimates of the component means are computed using

$$\mu_l^{(i+1)} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{T-1} \alpha^{(i)}(t_n) u_{ln}^{(i)}}{\sum_{n=0}^{T-1} (\alpha^{(i)}(t_n))^2 w_{ln}^{(i)}}. \quad (12)$$

Then, the component variances are re-estimated using

$$(\sigma_l^{(i+1)})^2 = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{T-1} v_{ln}^{(i)}}{\sum_{n=0}^{T-1} w_{ln}^{(i)}}. \quad (13)$$

The estimate of the modulation state vector sequence is obtained by solving a block tridiagonal system of linear equations akin to the Kalman smoothing filter. This system of equations is converted to a block upper triangular system of equations using Gaussian elimination (forward recursion). The estimates for the state vectors in \mathcal{A} are then calculated using back substitution (backward recursion).

The forward recursion begins by using the new estimates of $\{\mu_l^{(i)}\}$ and $\{\sigma_l^{(i)}\}$ to compute the "measure-

ment normalization coefficients"

$$x^{(i+1)}(t_n) = \sum_{l=1}^L \left(\frac{\mu_l^{(i+1)}}{\sigma_l^{(i+1)} K T_s} \right)^2 \pi_l^{(i)} w_{ln}^{(i)} \quad (14)$$

and the "measurements"

$$y^{(i+1)}(t_n) = \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{\mu_l^{(i+1)}}{(\sigma_l^{(i+1)})^2 K T_s} \pi_l^{(i)} w_{ln}^{(i)} \quad (15)$$

for $n = 0, \dots, \Upsilon - 1$. From these variables, the off-diagonal matrices $X_n^{(i+1)}$, the diagonal matrices $S_n^{(i+1)}$, the control matrices $U_n^{(i+1)}$ and the "measurement" matrices $Y_n^{(i+1)}$ are calculated for all valid n . The matrices X_n are obtained using the formula

$$X_n^{(i+1)} = Q^{-1} A + x^{(i+1)}(t_n) C^t C \quad (16)$$

for $n = 0, \dots, \Upsilon - 1$. The matrices $S_n^{(i+1)}$ are calculated from

$$S_n^{(i+1)} = Q_0^{-1} + A^t Q^{-1} A + x^{(i+1)}(t_n) C^t C \quad (17)$$

for $n = 0$,

$$S_n^{(i+1)} = Q^{-1} + A^t Q^{-1} A + x x C_n^{(i+1)} - x S x_{n-1}^{(i+1)} \quad (18)$$

for $0 < n < \Upsilon$ and

$$S_n^{(i+1)} = Q^{-1} + x^{(i+1)}(t_{n-1}) C^t C - x S x_{n-1}^{(i+1)} \quad (19)$$

for $n = \Upsilon$ where

$$x x C_n^{(i+1)} = (x^{(i+1)}(t_{n-1}) + x^{(i+1)}(t_n)) C^t C \quad (20)$$

and

$$x S x_n^{(i+1)} = X_n^{(i+1)} (S_n^{(i+1)})^{-1} (X_n^{(i+1)})^t. \quad (21)$$

The matrices $U_n^{(i+1)}$ are calculated from

$$U_n^{(i+1)} = Q_0^{-1} \bar{a} - A^t Q^{-1} b(t_n) \quad (22)$$

for $n = 0$,

$$U_n^{(i+1)} = Q^{-1} b(t_{n-1}) - A^t Q^{-1} b(t_n) + x S u_{n-1}^{(i+1)} \quad (23)$$

for $0 < n < \Upsilon$ and

$$U_n^{(i+1)} = Q^{-1} b(t_{n-1}) + x S u_{n-1}^{(i+1)} \quad (24)$$

for $n = \Upsilon$ where

$$x S u_n^{(i+1)} = X_n^{(i+1)} (S_n^{(i+1)})^{-1} U_n^{(i+1)}. \quad (25)$$

The matrices $Y_n^{(i+1)}$ are calculated using

$$Y_n^{(i+1)} = C^t y^{(i+1)}(t_n) \quad (26)$$

for $n = 0$,

$$Y_n^{(i+1)} = C^t (y^{(i+1)}(t_n) - y^{(i+1)}(t_{n-1})) - x S y_{n-1}^{(i+1)} \quad (27)$$

for $0 < n < \Upsilon$ and

$$Y_n^{(i+1)} = -C^t y^{(i+1)}(t_{n-1}) - x S y_{n-1}^{(i+1)} \quad (28)$$

for $n = \Upsilon$ where

$$x S y_n^{(i+1)} = X_n^{(i+1)} (S_n^{(i+1)})^{-1} Y_n^{(i+1)}. \quad (29)$$

This completes the forward recursion.

The backward recursion begins by solving for

$$a^{(i+1)}(t_\Upsilon) = -(S_\Upsilon^{(i+1)})^{-1} (Y_\Upsilon^{(i+1)} - U_\Upsilon^{(i+1)}). \quad (30)$$

The backward recursion

$$a^{(i+1)}(t_n) = -(S_n^{(i+1)})^{-1} (Y_n^{(i+1)} - U_n^{(i+1)}) + (S_n^{(i+1)})^{-1} (X_n^{(i+1)})^t a^{(i+1)}(t_{n+1}) \quad (31)$$

yields the estimates for the remaining elements in $\mathcal{A}^{(i+1)}$. Because each M-step of the generalized EM scheme increases the search function, $P(\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A}; \lambda^{(i+1)}) \geq P(\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A}; \lambda^{(i)})$. The generalized EM iteration is repeated until

$$\frac{\log[P(\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A}; \lambda^{(i+1)})] - \log[P(\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A}; \lambda^{(i)})]}{1 + \log[P(\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A}; \lambda^{(i+1)})]} < \epsilon \quad (32)$$

for some desired $\epsilon > 0$.

6 Algorithm Comparison

The performance of this EM algorithm was compared to the performance of the adaptive comb filter (ACF) described in reference [8] and the extended Kalman filter (EKF) described in references [10] and [3] ([3] was used to turn the real EKF described in [10] into a complex EKF). To compare these three algorithms, 100 Monte Carlo trials were performed using a complex GFM signal in complex Gaussian noise. The same complex GFM signal, $s(t) = A \sum_{l=1}^5 \exp[i2\pi\sqrt{l} f_o m(t)]$, was used in all 100 trials. Observe that this GFM signal's carrier function is almost periodic. Since the ACF and the EKF assume that the carrier function is periodic, each of these algorithms estimated the parameters of a periodic carrier function consisting of 25 components where the initial estimate of the fundamental frequency (one over the period) was about $f_o/10$. The SNR for all the Monte Carlo trials was set to 10dB where the SNR was defined as $10 \log[5A^2]$. For each Monte Carlo trial, 8193 samples from $s(t)$ were added to 8193 samples of three independent zero mean, unit variance, complex white Gaussian noise sequences to obtain independent noisy signals for each algorithm. Because the ACF can only process real data, the ACF was fed the real part of its complex noisy signals.

The modulation function of $s(t)$ was chosen as

$$m(t) = t + \frac{\Delta}{2\pi f_o} \int_0^t f(x) dx \quad (33)$$

where $f_o = 0.08$, $f(t)$ was the output of a second order autoregressive (AR) filter with poles at $0.995e^{\pm 2\pi/10000}$ driven by zero mean real white Gaussian noise with variance 2.0263×10^{-10} , and the modulation index Δ was equal to 0.25. 16384 samples were collected from the AR filter, and the first 8191 samples were dropped to eliminate the transient response. The remaining 8193 samples were used to generate 8193 samples from $s(t)$.

Each algorithm requires different initial parameter settings, but the initial parameter settings for the EM algorithm and the ACF are closely related to the initial parameter settings for the complex EKF. Consequently, initial parameter estimates for the EM algorithm and the ACF were generated from a starting vector obtained from the initialization procedure for the complex EKF. The initialization procedure for the EKF was based on the initialization discussion in [10]. The implementation of the ACF followed the recommendations of reference [8] for high SNR signals.

The EM estimation algorithm was initialized as follows. The DFT size was chosen as $K = 128$, and a uniform PDF was used model the normalized power spectrum of the noise. The mixing proportions and means were initialized using the same random method as was used for the EKF. The variances of the five Gaussian component PDFs were set 128^{-2} . A second order kinematic model was used to model the state evolution of the modulation function where the control input sequence was set to $\{[128, 0]^t\}$ and the scale of the process covariance matrix was 1.6839×10^{-7} . The initial estimate of the state vector was a ramp function. The stopping tolerance ϵ was set to 10^{-6} .

The ACF did not produce any reasonable parameter estimates. The complex EKF produced good results as did the EM algorithm. The mean estimates with their 95% confidence intervals for the component amplitudes (25 in this case) from the complex EKF appear in figure 1; only, the amplitudes estimates for components 10, 14, 17, 20, and 22 correspond to actual components. The mean amplitude estimates \pm the 95% confidence intervals obtained by the EM algorithm are $1.3420 \pm 2.4622 \times 10^{-3}$, $1.3640 \pm 3.2685 \times 10^{-3}$, $1.3956 \pm 4.9724 \times 10^{-3}$, $1.3916 \pm 2.0636 \times 10^{-2}$ and $1.3800 \pm 9.9907 \times 10^{-3}$. The actual amplitude values in $s(t)$ were all equal to the $\sqrt{2}$. Clearly, both methods produced biased estimates; however, the complex EKF produces more biased estimates.

The estimates of the modulation sequence from the complex EKF and the EM algorithm are not directly

comparable because the complex EKF assumes the signal has a periodic carrier function. Therefore, figure 2 plots the correlation coefficient between the true modulation sequence and the estimate modulation sequence from the complex EKF and the EM algorithm. From figure 1, it is quite evident that the EM algorithm produces a better estimate of the modulation sequence because the EM algorithm's correlation coefficient is almost always larger than the complex EKF, and the sequence of correlation coefficients from the EM algorithm has fewer outliers.

7 Summary

This paper described a new algorithm based on the EM method for estimating the parameters of a GFM signal in noise and the SNR. This new algorithm does not need to know a GFM signal's harmonic ratios. The comparison of the EM algorithm to the ACF and the complex EKF show that the EM algorithm has superior performance when estimating the parameters of GFM signals with aperiodic carrier functions. A more detailed performance analysis using GFM signals with periodic and aperiodic carriers including comparisons to the algorithms described in references [8], [10] and [3] is available in [5].

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Figure 1: The average amplitude estimates from the complex EKF with the 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 2: The correlation coefficients between the actual modulation sequence and the estimated modulation sequences from the EM algorithm (dash dot line) and the complex EKF (dashed line).

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